

Investigation of a Kuwait Crude Oil

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In this paper a short review is given of the principles applied in the graphical statistical analysis of crude oil fractions. Applications are shown in the characterization of a Kuwait crude. The correlation between distinct physical constants and the chemical structure of a number of fractions of the crude is demonstrated by comparing experimental physical data with data, predicted by means of proper relations¹.

Principles of Graphical Statistical Analysis of Mineral Oils

Mineral oils consist chiefly of complicated mixtures of hydrocarbons; distinct amounts of sulphur, nitrogen, and oxygen compounds and small quantities of organo-metallic compounds may be present as well. The hydrocarbons belong to the following groups:

- (a) The paraffins, saturated noncyclic molecules in which branchings may be present.
- (b) The naphthenes, consisting mainly of saturated cyclopentane and cyclohexane derivatives.
- (c) The aromatics.

Olefinic hydrocarbons are generally absent in natural crudes; they may play an important role in cracked products of any kind.

For the low-boiling fractions (up to the gasoline range) the distinction between these groups is quite sharp. Application of modern separation methods (distillation, chromatography, etc.) enables a reliable quantitative separation of the groups mentioned; the isolation and identification of *individual* hydrocarbons, however, requires elaborate and time-consuming research. Complete separations have been executed in a few cases only².

In mineral oil fractions of higher molecular weight the total number of different hydrocarbon molecules is extremely high and with a few exceptions the separation and identification of individual molecules are not possible by the existing methods. In the hydrocarbon molecules paraffinic, naphthenic, and aromatic elements may be linked together and therefore these molecules may possess paraffinic, naphthenic and aromatic properties in a ratio which to a certain extent will be determined by the proportion of the respective structures. Thus, to solve the problem of analysis of these fractions it is necessary to deal with the oil fractions *statistically*³. These are considered to be built up of a limited number of structural elements which are related to an *average molecule*, a hypothetical molecule, representing the average nature of all the individual molecules present in the mixture.

The following quantities are normally taken into account:

- R_N , the number of rings per average molecule in naphthenic structure.
 R_A , the number of aromatic rings per average molecule in aromatic structure.
 $R_T = R_A + R_N$, the total number of rings per average molecule.
 $\%C_N = \%$ carbon atoms present in naphthenic structure.
 $\%C_A = \%$ Carbon atoms present in aromatic structure.
 $\%C_P = \%$ Carbon atoms present in paraffinic structure.
 $\%C_R = \%$ $C_A + \%C_N$, $\%$ carbon atoms present in ring structure.

A further important structural quantity is Φ , the degree of branching of the mixture, which is especially of interest in the study of isomerization phenomena⁴; for the investigation of aromatic fractions it is sometimes useful in distinguishing different types of aromatic molecules, e.g. monoaromatic rings, diaromatic rings, etc.⁵

For the direct quantitative estimation of the structural elements of mineral oil fractions, use can be made of the so-called "direct method", which is based on a quantitative analytical hydrogenation of the fraction to be investigated and accurate ultimate analyses and molecular weight determinations of both the original and the hydrogenated samples. This method, which has been described in detail in the literature,⁶ allows the unambiguous determination of $\%C_A$ and R_T ; to calculate R_A from $\%C_A$ and $\%C_R$ from R_T an assumption has to be made concerning the type of the rings and their manner of fusion; normally it is assumed that the rings, when present, are *six-membered* and *kata-condensed*, which assumptions seem to be justified by practical experience.

The direct method is very laborious and time-consuming. It can only be executed by highly skilled analysts. Since it is the only unambiguous and independent method for the analysis of crude oil fractions, it should always be employed in cases of doubt. Actually all reliable empirical methods, which have been developed for the investigation of mineral oil fractions and which are based on empirical relations of distinct physical properties, have been checked by the absolute *direct method*.

Waterman ring analysis.—This method can be considered to be the first reliable one for the analysis of mineral oil fractions and it is based on the empirical fact that for saturated hydrocarbons or hydrocarbon mixtures, there exists a linear relationship between hydrogen content and specific refraction, r^{20}_{spec} :

$$r^{20}_{\text{spec}} = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot 1/d = 0.20133 + 0.00890 \%H$$

in which n = refractive index (n_D^{20}), d = density (d_4^{20}), and $\%H$ = hydrogen content.

This relationship made it possible the analysis of *saturated* mineral oil fractions to replace the difficult and laborious ultimate analysis by a simple estimation of refractive index and density and to estimate R_N *graphically* by means of a simple *ring-analysis diagram*⁷. For the analysis of *aromatic* samples Vlugter *et al.* developed a method⁸ based on data of specific refraction, molecular weight and aniline point; later on Leendertse⁹ succeeded in developing a graphical method in which only *three* physical constants: refractive index, density, and molecular weight were sufficient to determine $\%C_A$, $\%C_R$, $\%C_N$, and the corresponding ring numbers.

Leendertse's method was worked out mathematically by Tadema, who correlated data of a large number of crude oil fractions of different origin and gave a final form to the ring analysis method in the formulas of the *n-d-M*-method^{6,9} which nowadays have found general acceptance in the petroleum industry.

Later investigations demonstrated the applicability of viscosity data for the analysis of mineral oil fractions. The *v-n-d* method and the *viscosity-ncmogram method*¹¹ are based on kinematic viscosity, refractive index, and density and allow also the approximate estimation of the molecular weight from the physical constants mentioned.

For the estimation of the *degree of branching* ϕ (the average number of branchings per molecule) of saturated mineral oil fractions, Waterman and Leendertse¹² developed an empirical graphical method, based on data of the specific refraction and the specific parachor p^{20}_{spec} :

$$p^{20}_{\text{spec}} = \frac{\gamma^2}{d}$$

The diagram of Waterman and Leendertse was improved and revised in later publications¹³. For the estimation of ϕ in aromatic fractions a more general diagram has been developed recently¹⁴, based on formulas of De Booij¹⁵. It should be emphasized, however, that the various methods of branching analysis have only a qualitative, or at best semi-quantitative meaning. Because reliable absolute methods for branching analysis of hydrocarbon mixtures fail, the estimation of the degree of branching by the existing empirical methods is of some value only in comparative studies, but lacks any absolute significance.

Correlations of Physical Constants of Mineral Oils

As has been shown in the preceding paragraph, in principle three different physical constants are necessary for the ring-type analysis of mineral oil fractions, e.g. *n*, *d*, and *M* or *v*, *n*, and *d* etc.

As a matter of fact, it can be expected that it must be possible to predict distinct physical properties of mineral oil fractions from properly chosen other physical constants. In the Delft Technological University extensive research has been carried out to confirm this and to develop practical and useful correlations which allow the mutual prediction of important physical data e.g.,

(a) Prediction of (a) average molecular weight from kinematic viscosity, refractive index, and density¹⁶; (b) Prediction of surface of tension σ from kinematic viscosity and density¹⁶; (c) Prediction of ultrasonic sound velocity *U* from kinematic viscosity, density, and refractive index¹⁷; (d) kinematic viscosity of mineral oil fractions at an arbitrary temperature (70°) from the kinematic viscosity at 20°, the refractive index and the density¹⁸; and the simple relationship¹⁹ (e) between ultrasonic sound velocity and surface tension of mineral oil fractions:

$$\sigma = 0.0354 \eta - 20.6$$

In the next paragraph the application of these relationships has been demonstrated and compared against experimental on the data of a number of Kuwait crude oil fractions, in the next section.

Experimental Procedures

Distillation.—A preliminary distillation showed that the crude to be investigated did not contain products boiling in the gasoline range.

Small amounts of water, present in the crude, were removed by treatment with anhydrous sodium sulphate and occasional stirring.

The dried crude oil was distilled in a vacuum equipment at approx. 1 mm. Hg; ten fractions were collected at increasing distillation temperatures. The distillation residue (59% of the crude) was submitted to molecular distillation in a falling film apparatus²⁰; in this way two more distillation fractions were obtained. The final residue (30.5% of the original crude), which was collected as a tarry mass, was not further investigated. Some data of the obtained fractions are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Distillation of Kuwait crude oil.

Fraction.	Wt. % of crude.	Boiling range.	Av. M.W.	%S.	Colour.	Consistency.
1	4.2	65—108°/5mm.	187	0.16	Colorless	Liquid
2	3.5	108— 30°/5	199	0.32	„	„
3	4.4	130— 48°/5	222	0.47	Slightly yellow	„
4	3.9	148— 58°/5	237	0.60	„	„
5	4.2	158— 68°/5	251	0.84	Yellow	„
6	4.0	163— 74°/1	270	1.12	Brown-yellow	„
7	4.0	174— 84°/1	289	1.20	Brown	„
8	4.2	184— 92°/1	295	1.22	„	„
9	4.3	192—200°/1	334	1.21	„	Pasty
10	4.5	200—205°/1	337	1.26	„	Semi-solid
11	18.0	Molecular distillation	467	1.53	Dark brown	„
12	10.3	Do	622	1.76	„	„
Residue	30.5	..	..	2.82	Nearly black	Tarry

Hydrogenation.—The fractions 1-10 were hydrogenated quantitatively in rotating autoclaves using nickel on kieselguhr as a catalyst at 300° as a maximum and a hydrogen pressure of 150-300 atmospheres. This analytical hydrogenation aims at a complete saturation of the oil fractions and simultaneous removal of foreign elements (sulphur) without further drastic structural changes of the oil molecules; thus a comparative study of the original fractions and their hydrogenation products, in which the aromatic rings have been transformed quantitatively into the corresponding naphthenes, becomes possible.

Table II records a review of the physical data, which were determined of the different fractions and their hydrogenation products in view of the application of different methods for the determination of their chemical structure.

TABLE II
Physical constants of Kuwait crude oil fractions and their hydrogenation products.

Fraction.	η_{sp}^0 .	d_{40}^{20} .	Av. M.W.	%S.	$\log_{20}$.	Kinematic viscosity (centistokes)			Surface tension (dyne/cm) 20°.	Ultrasonic sound velocity (m/sec.,) 20°.	r_{sp}^{20} spec.	β_{sp}^{20} spec.
						$\log_{20}$.	$\log_{40}$.	$\log_{70}$.				
1	1.4799	0.859	187	0.16	0.485	0.314	0.116	—	25.4	1328	0.3307	2.613
1 hydr.	1.4550	0.828	—	—	0.458	—	—	—	27.9	1356	0.3277	2.776
2	1.4879	0.873	199	0.32	0.663	0.444	0.222	—	27.5	1403	0.3300	2.623
2 hydr.	1.4600	0.840	—	—	0.630	—	—	—	28.8	1380	0.3261	2.758
3	1.4898	0.877	222	0.47	0.806	0.576	0.322	—	28.6	1414	0.3295	2.637
3 hydr.	1.4620	0.843	—	—	0.774	—	—	—	29.0	1385	0.3261	2.753
4	1.4905	0.880	237	0.60	0.978	0.713	0.424	—	29.9	1423	0.3288	2.657
4 hydr.	1.4638	0.841	—	—	0.828	—	—	—	28.7	1389	0.3280	2.752
5	1.4978	0.892	251	0.84	1.176	0.863	0.535	—	30.5	1438	0.3285	2.635
5 hydr.	1.4679	0.853	—	—	1.020	—	—	—	29.5	1410	0.3258	2.732
6	1.5066	0.908	270	1.12	1.319	0.974	0.587	—	30.9	1453	0.3275	2.597
6 hydr.	1.4773	0.864	—	—	1.031	—	—	—	30.1	1418	0.3272	2.711
7	1.5099	0.912	289	1.20	1.667	1.247	0.819	—	31.5	1469	0.3279	2.598
7 hydr.	1.4756	0.871	—	—	1.469	—	—	—	30.5	1444	0.3296	2.698
8	1.5120	0.916	295	1.22	1.777	1.345	0.866	—	31.7	1475	0.3276	2.590
8 hydr.	1.4760	0.870	—	—	1.454	—	—	—	30.5	1441	0.3242	2.701
9	1.5164	0.924	334	1.21	1.99**	1.507	1.004	0.670	—	—	—	—
9 hydr.	1.4802	0.880	—	—	1.73**	1.333	0.887	0.593	—	—	—	—
10	1.5211	0.931	337	1.26	2.16**	1.628	1.088	0.736	—	—	—	—
10 hydr.	1.4823	0.885	—	—	1.84**	1.396	0.939	0.640	—	—	—	—
11	1.5192*	0.926*	467	1.53	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
11 hydr.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
12	1.5332*	0.952*	622	1.76	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
12 hydr.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

* 70°C

** Extrapolated

Structural Analysis.—Structural analysis of the oil fractions was performed by two different methods, namely the n - d - M ⁹ and ν - n - d method¹⁰; the latter also allowed the approximate estimation of the molecular weight.

To estimate the average number of branchings per molecule, ϕ , the general diagram¹⁴ has been applied. The results of the analyses have been collected in Table III.

Correlations of Physical Constants.—In Table IV the results of some experimental and predicted physical properties of the Kuwait oil fractions are summarized.

TABLE IV

Comparison of experimental physical data of Kuwait oil fractions with data predicted from other physical constants.

Fraction.	Molecular weight.		Surface tension (dyne/cm) at 20°.		Log. kinem. visc. at 70° (centistokes).		Ultrasonic sound velocity (m/sec.).		Surface tension (dyne/cm) at 20°.	
	Exp.	*Predicted ¹⁰ .	Exp.	*Predicted ¹⁶ .	Exp.	*Predicted ¹⁸ .	Exp.	*Predicted ¹⁷ .	Exp.	**Predicted ¹⁹ .
1	187	190	25.4	28.3	0.12	0.12	1382	1375	25.4	28.4
1 h	—	190	27.9	27.5	—	—	1356	1342	27.9	27.4
2	199	205	27.5	29.2	0.22	0.22	1403	1398	27.5	29.6
2h	—	205	28.8	28.2	—	—	1380	1363	28.8	28.3
3	222	215	28.6	29.6	0.32	0.32	1414	1410	28.6	29.5
3h	—	220	29.0	28.6	—	—	1385	1376	29.0	28.5
4	237	235	29.9	29.9	0.42	0.42	1423	1421	29.9	29.8
4h	—	235	28.7	28.7	—	—	1389	1381	28.7	28.6
5	251	245	30.5	30.5	0.54	0.54	1438	1437	30.5	30.2
5h	—	250	29.5	29.3	—	—	1410	1400	29.5	29.4
6	270	255	30.9	31.1	0.59	0.61	1453	1450	30.9	30.9
6h	—	240	30.1	29.7	—	—	1418	1409	30.1	29.6
7	299	290	31.5	31.2	0.82	0.82	1469	1464	31.5	31.4
7 h	—	290	30.5	30.3	—	—	1444	1428	30.5	30.6
8	295	300	31.7	31.5	0.87	0.87	1475	1470	31.7	31.7
8 h	—	295	30.5	30.3	—	—	1441	1440	30.5	30.4
9	334	320	—	—	1.00	1.01	—	—	—	—
9h	—	320	—	—	0.89	0.85	—	—	—	—
10	337	325	—	—	1.09	1.11	—	—	—	—
10 h	—	325	—	—	0.94	0.90	—	—	—	—

*From $\log \nu_{20}$, n_D^{20} , d_4^{20} .

†From $\log \nu^{20}$ and d_4^{20} .

**From ultrasonic sound velocity.

As follows from Table I, the Kuwait crude oil under investigation did not contain lower boiling fractions. Approximately 40% of weight of the crude could be distilled in vacuum (boiling point $< 205^\circ$ at 1 mm Hg), another 20% of weight of the crude was distilled molecularly. The sulphur content of the crude was relatively high (1.60% S); in the distillation fractions the weight% sulphur gradually increased from 0.16% in the lowest boiling fraction to 2.82% in the distillation residue.

The composition of the different oil fractions, as determined by the n - d - M method and the ν - n - d -method, show a remarkable constancy. Approximately 50% of carbon atoms are

present in paraffinic chains, approximately 25% in naphthenic rings and approximately 25% in aromatic rings and these figures show slight differences at increasing molecular weight of the fractions (compare Table III).

The results of the π - d - M and the ν - n - d methods for the structural analysis of the oil fractions agree reasonably well. The data of the hydrogenated fractions show that hydrogenation is not complete in the case of the fractions 4 and 6.

The average number of branchings in the fractions is very small, even in the higher boiling fractions Φ does not exceed 3 per molecule. It should, however, be stressed that the determination of branchings, particularly in original oil fractions, has only a semi-quantitative character.

As follows from Table IV, several physical properties of the oil fractions, such as the average molecular weight, the surface tension, the ultrasonic sound velocity, and the kinematic viscosity at arbitrary temperatures, can be predicted with a reasonable accuracy from data of the kinematic viscosity at 20°, the refractive index (n_D^{20}) and the density (d_4^{20}). It should be remarked that several diagrams which are applied to predict the physical properties mentioned, have only been developed for straight-run fractions and may show small deviations when applied for saturated (hydrogenated) fractions. Besides, the surface tension is highly influenced by the presence of small amounts of surface-active impurities; this might explain the differences between the experimental values of the surface tension and the values predicted from kinematic viscosity and density on one hand, and from ultrasonic sound velocity on the other; it is at least remarkable that the values of the surface tension, predicted by both these completely independent methods, show such a close agreement (compare Table IV).

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